

PREDICTION OF DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE CYLINDERS AFTER IMPACT

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ABSTRACT : This paper presents results from a study in two parts. The first involves the identification and modelling of damage initiation and development in composite cylinders subjected to drop weight impact. The second is concerned with the evaluation of the influence of this damage on residual strength under hydrostatic pressure loading. The improved understanding of these phenomena and the development of predictive tools is part of an ongoing effort to improve the long term integrity of composite structures for underwater applications.

KEYWORDS : Impact, Damage, Filament winding, Delamination

INTRODUCTION

The use of composites for underwater applications (underwater vehicles, oceanography, sub-sea installations for oil production...) is very attractive, both for weight savings and improved corrosion resistance. The main loading of such structures is hydrostatic pressure, which increases with immersion depth, but damage tolerance is also a key parameter. Impact damage may occur either during handling or in service. Impact behaviour of glass/epoxy cylinders has received much less attention than impact of flat panels but some previous studies have been reported. For example Swanson [1] and Kistler [2] compared strains measured on carbon/epoxy cylinders with results from model predictions. Impact damage models have been presented for composite cylinders by Zou [3] and Krishnamurthy [4]. Alderson and Evans [5,6] looked at damage in glass/epoxy cylinders and correlated impact damage with damage in static loading tests. Kim [7] studied the effect of curvature on impact damage and concluded that damage areas increase with increasing curvature.

The present study differs from previous work in that it is the influence of impact damage on hydrostatic pressure resistance which is of interest here. Very few studies have treated this aspect of damage tolerance. The development of damage mechanisms are studied first, in order to be able to take them into account in a model of residual strength. The outline of the project is shown in Figure 1. In the present paper the first part of the study, the description of impact damage and associated modelling will be described. Some indications of how this damage affects the capacity of cylinders to resist external pressure loading will also be presented.

Figure 1. Overview of project.

MATERIALS

The materials examined in the study were all manufactured using the filament winding process. E-glass fibers were impregnated with a low viscosity epoxy resin LY556/HY905/DY061 from Vantico. These cylinders were cured at 125°C for 7 hours and measured fiber volume fraction V_f was 62%. Porosity is about 10%. The cylinders used have an internal diameter of 55 mm and a wall thickness of 6.5 mm and were wet wound at an angle of $\pm 55^\circ$ to the cylinder axis. Samples for impact and pressure testing are 110 mm long. Micrographic observations show a $[\pm 55]_{10}$ stacking sequence lay-up. Material properties are shown in Table 1.

Material	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	ν_{12}
Glass/epoxy ply 0°	49.5 GPa	15.9 GPa	5.6 GPa	0.255

Table 1. Material properties used for modelling.

FINITE ELEMENT (FE) MODELLING

The models presented were run using ABAQUS version 6.2 [8]. Shell elements with reduced integration (S4R) available in the library were used with geometric nonlinearity. Based on microscopic observations, the tube thickness was modelled as a laminated cylindrical shell with transversely isotropic plies. The impactor, plate and cradle were considered as rigid bodies and were taken as the “master surface”. The potential contact area of the cylinder was taken as a “slave surface” so the individual nodes of the composite cylinder were constrained not to penetrate the surfaces of the rigid bodies whereas the contrary was permitted due to the higher stiffness of the latter. The relative motions of the contact surfaces were modelled as “small sliding”, which assumes that contact surfaces do not move very much relative to each other [9]. The contact algorithm used is based on the penalty method. Also, a particular contact law is implemented to reproduce local hertzian contact effects during the quasi-static indentation phase. Damage was not taken into account numerically in this study.

TEST-MODEL COMPARISONS

In order to be able to model the damage development during impact correctly the impact event has been first decomposed and the different contributions have been examined separately. These include:

- global elastic crushing, governed by the elastic properties of the cylinder

- local indentation of the cylinder wall and the generation of Hertzian contact stresses
- combination of these two global and local effects in cylinder indentation
- impact behaviour.

The first three were examined under static loading conditions, in order to verify that the complete behaviour could be modelled and to characterise damage development, before considering the dynamic behaviour. These will now be considered separately and some examples of the correlation between model predictions and test results will be given.

1. Global crushing

Figure 2 shows the test used to examine global crushing. The main aim of this test is to verify the input properties for the finite element (FE) modelling, also shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows an example of the correlation between the model and measured stiffness. There is a small initial bedding in displacement which is not modelled but thereafter the correlation is quite satisfactory.

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Figure 3. Test-model correlation, transverse crush test.

2. Local cylinder wall indentation

Local indentation was studied by pushing the hemispherical steel impactor (the same one as that used in the subsequent impact tests, diameter 50 mm) into the composite cylinder mounted on a rigid steel mandrel which was machined to fit the cylinder. This allows the indentation response of the curved surface to be determined without the global cylinder flexural response. Figure 4 shows the experimental set-up and results. The local response causes very little damage to the cylinder apart from some whitening of the resin top-coat (0.3 mm).

Figure 4. Indentation test set-up and load-displacement plots from tests on 4 cylinders.

These tests enabled a contact law to be established, using the loading-unloading approach of Tan & Sun [10]. For loading stage, $f = k \cdot \alpha^n$ (1) and for unloading stage, $f = f_m \left(\frac{\alpha - \alpha_0}{\alpha_m - \alpha_0} \right)^p$.

α is the depth of indentation. α_m is the indentation corresponding to the maximum contact force f_m . $\alpha_0 = 0$ when $\alpha_m < \alpha_{cr}$ and $\alpha_0 = \alpha_m \left[1 - \left(\frac{\alpha_{cr}}{\alpha_m} \right)^p \right]$ when $\alpha_m \geq \alpha_{cr}$. The tests provided the following parameters fitted from the local cylinder indentation curves above. $\alpha_{cr} = 0.35 \text{ mm}$ is the critical indentation. $k = 3.7 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^n$ is the local contact stiffness where $n = 2.1$ and $p = 3.2$.

The expression for $k = \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} + \frac{1}{2R_{cyl}} \right)^{-1/2} \left/ \left(\frac{(1-\nu_i)^2}{E_i} + \frac{1}{E_2} \right) \right.$ given by Chandrashekara [11] when spherical and cylindrical bodies are in contact, with $n = 1.5$ did not permit a suitable fitting for the material used. Subscript i is for the impactor and cyl for the composite cylinder.

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3. Quasi-static cylinder indentation

The next step was to examine whether the results from the two previous steps would allow the response of the cylinder under loading which combined local and global effects to be determined. This corresponds to a quasi-static version of the impact test. The cylinder was placed in the cradle used for impact testing and the impactor was pushed into it. Figure 5 shows the test set-up and model.

Figure 5. Cylinder indentation, test and FE model.

The contact force (1) has allowed the evolution of the contact pressure (2) during crushing to be determined by dividing the contact force by the projected surface of the impactor during the indentation:

$$p = \frac{k}{\pi} \frac{\alpha^{n-1}}{2r_i - \alpha} \quad (2).$$

Figure 6 shows the response and prediction. This has resulted in a very good correlation. After the threshold indentation value is reached, around 5700 N corresponding to 4 Joules, extensive damage is introduced.

Figure 6. Prediction and test results.

Figure 7. Example of damage observed, applied energy 36 J.

4. Impact

Finally the impact test was studied. An instrumented drop-weight fixture was designed, Figure 8, enabling single impacts to be applied to cylinders without rebound and measurements to be made of impactor acceleration and speed.

Figure 8. Instrumented drop weight set-up.

A series of impact tests was performed on 40 cylinders. A new cylinder was impacted for each test, using a 1.6 kg 50 mm diameter hemispherical steel impactor. The impact energy was varied by increasing drop height. A piezoelectric accelerometer from Endevco is fixed into the impactor and gives acceleration signal $a(t)$ which is directly proportional to the impact force (3). The impactor's displacement $x(t)$ is obtained by double integration of the acceleration signal (4).

$$f(t) = m_i a(t) \quad (3), \quad x(t) = \int_0^{T_c} \left(V_i + \int_0^{T_c} a(t) dt \right) dt \quad (4).$$

m_i is the impactor mass, the acceleration, T_c contact duration and V_i the speed just before impact. For low energy impacts no damage was observed. An example of the recorded force and displacement versus time plot for one of these non-damaging impacts is shown in Figure 9, together with a model prediction.

Figure 9. Force versus time plots, measured and predicted, 3 J impact.

At higher impact energies (4 Joules and above) extensive whitening was noted. This threshold level is similar to that observed in quasi-static cylinder indentation tests. Ultrasonic inspection enabled projected damage areas to be measured for all test specimens, Figure 10. Then samples were sectioned to determine through-thickness damage and an example of section through an impacted cylinder is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10. Projected damage area from ultrasonic inspection after impact (three cylinder specimens per energy level) and examples of damaged cylinders.

It is interesting to compare damage generated in static indentation tests with that in drop weight impact. To a first approximation these are reasonably similar for similar energy levels. Figure 11 shows an example of damage for a 24 Joule impact. Olsson has discussed the limits between quasi-static (large mass) and dynamic (wave controlled) impacts, and proposed a criterion for plates based on the ratio impactor mass/plate mass [12]. Here the impactor is over 5 times heavier than the target and a quasi-static response would be expected.

Figure 11. Axial section through impact damaged cylinder wall, 24 J, penetrant and U.V. lighting.

DAMAGE MODELLING

The tests and models described above provide the basis for the next step, which is to develop damage prediction models. One approach is to use FE models. This is not a trivial exercise but is currently being pursued. Dynamic explicit finite element codes are now widely used to model the response of structures under projectile impact [13]. Representing the contact or contact-impact between subsystems through the method of Lagrange multipliers is a major modelling step in order to obtain a

representative response of the experimental set-up. In the explicit finite element code, several formulations of the Lagrange multipliers method are possible. In the case of laminated structures, the contact technique can be used on a global scale to model the stress evolution versus time, and on a "mesoscale" to model the delamination between plies as a function of the volume damage on both sides of the interface. An example of the modelling of delamination development under impact loading in circular ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) plates, is given in reference [14].

Such models require considerable computer power due to the fine meshing and short time increments needed. A second approach is to develop simpler analytical approximate models, which lack the detail of the numerical approach but which enable engineering estimations to be made and which can indicate promising directions for improved performance. From the damage characterization it is clear that extensive delaminations occur during impact. The use of an energy balance model (5) may therefore be useful, and a simple approach is to assume that the loss in energy of the impactor during a drop weight impact is entirely used to create delaminations and that the loading is pure shear :

$$\frac{1}{2} m_i V_i^2 = G_{IIc} (\sum A_i) \quad (5)$$

where G_{IIc} the critical mode II strain energy release rate and A_i the crack surface created at each interface. If we plot the impact energy as a function of the total crack surface area (estimated from sections of samples together with ultrasonic maps of the impact damage forms) we obtain Figure 12. This plot enables predicted damage area to be compared to measured results, using a value of G_{IIc} of 1570 J/m^2 obtained from tests developed specifically to measure quasi-static mode II fracture toughness of curved laminates [15]. The prediction is quite promising given the simplifying assumptions and the slopes of the predicted and measured crack area are quite similar in this energy range.

Figure 12. Crack surface area versus net impact energy.

To extend this type of analysis further it is necessary to take account of the influence of fibre orientation on crack resistance. For example, fibres at $\pm 55^\circ$ (in the axial direction of the cylinder) are significantly more resistant to delamination propagation than those at $\pm 35^\circ$ (the hoop direction) but a crack propagating in the hoop direction also encounters the cylinder curvature. The G_{IIc} value taken to plot Figure 12 is the mean of values for the $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 55^\circ$ directions. The form of the damage observed suggests that cracks meet less resistance in the axial direction, in spite of the greater fibre angle in this direction. Another factor to consider is the rate dependence of these G_{IIc} values, published results suggest that the rate dependence of mode II delamination may be significant, tending to increase with higher loading rates [16]. This would reduce the predicted delamination area this

work on simple physical models is continuing as it may enable the impact resistance potential of new material combinations to be evaluated using relatively inexpensive tests.

INFLUENCE OF DAMAGE ON RESISTANCE TO HYDROSTATIC PRESSURE

The second part of the study involves the evaluation of the influence of impact damage on the resistance of composite cylinders to hydrostatic pressure. Tests have been performed at the hydrostatic pressure testing facility at IFREMER. Cylinder ends were protected with specially designed aluminium end caps. First, cylinders without impact damage were tested, increasing pressure at 12 bars/minute to failure, which occurred at pressures above 100 MPa (equivalent to 10 km immersion depth). Then tests were performed on cylinders impacted at different energy levels. Figure 13 shows the residual implosion pressure versus impact energy. This indicates a significant loss of pressure resistance for quite low impact energies.

Figure 13. Residual implosion pressure after impact.

Figure 13 also shows examples of cylinders after implosion. The impact damage clearly initiates premature failure. It is very important to be able to relate these results to other cylinder dimensions and this is an essential element of a predictive model. Some preliminary tests on scale effects were presented previously [17], more work on this aspect is also underway.

IMPROVING DAMAGE TOLERANCE

The ultimate aim of this work is to improve the damage tolerance of underwater pressure vessels. Glass/reinforced composites are used today for oceanography (messenger systems, instrumentation pods and protective housings) and submarine structures (outer casings, sonar domes). More extensive applications are possible including autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) or submersible pressure cases and offshore structures. However, it is apparent from the results above that impact damage can reduce the implosion resistance of these cylinders significantly even when the apparent damage area is quite small (less than 5% of the cylinder surface). Many alternative fibres, orientations, and matrix materials are possible but the damage tolerance tests necessary to evaluate all combinations are excessively expensive and time consuming. By running impact damage and residual implosion pressure models validated by a small number of tests this process can be greatly accelerated.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents results from an ongoing project to study the damage tolerance of composite cylinders for underwater applications. Models have been developed to simulate the dynamic response of such cylinders, work is now concentrating on implementing damage criteria in these models. Impact damage has been shown to reduce the residual implosion strength of glass/epoxy cylinders significantly. A 12 Joule impact reduces implosion pressure by 40%. This provides a great incentive for the development of structures with improved damage tolerance.

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